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***Spiribacter aquaticus* sp. nov., a new member of the genus *Spiribacter* from Santa
Pola saltern**

María José León¹, Borja Aldeguer-Riquelme², Josefa Antón², Cristina Sánchez-Porro¹
and Antonio Ventosa¹

¹Department of Microbiology and Parasitology, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of
Sevilla, 41012 Sevilla, Spain

²Department of Physiology, Genetics and Microbiology, University of Alicante, Alicante,
Spain

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*Corresponding author. Tel: +34 954556765; fax: +34 954628162.

E-mail address: ventosa@us.es (A. Ventosa).

The GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession number for the 16S rRNA gene sequence of
Spiribacter aquaticus SP30^T is LT714150.

26 A moderately halophilic bacterium, designated as strain SP30^T was isolated from a
27 solar saltern located in Santa Pola, Alicante, in the East coast of Spain. It was a
28 Gram-stain-negative, strictly aerobic bacterium, able to grow at 7.5-25 % (w/v)
29 NaCl and optimally at 12.5 % (w/v) NaCl. Phylogenetic analyses based on the 16S
30 rRNA gene sequences showed that the new isolate is a member of the genus
31 *Spiribacter*, being the most closely related species *Spiribacter roseus* SSL50^T (99.9 %
32 sequence similarity) and *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T (99.4 %). The 16S rRNA
33 gene sequence similarity with the type species *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T was 96.6
34 %. The level of DNA-DNA relatedness between strain SP30^T and the species *S.*
35 *roseus* SSL50^T and *S. curvatus* UAH-SP71^T was 40 %, and 55 %, respectively, being
36 these values lower than the 70 % threshold accepted for species delineation. The
37 major fatty acids were C_{16:0}, C_{18:1 ω7c}, C_{19:0 cyclo ω8c} and C_{12:0}. Similarly to other
38 species of *Spiribacter*, curved rods and spiral cells are observed for strain SP30^T, and
39 the metabolic versatility is reduced to the utilization of few organic compounds as
40 sole carbon and energy source; however, it differs on the colony pigmentation
41 (brownish yellow instead pink) and a higher growth rate. Based on these data and
42 on the phenotypic, genotypic, and chemotaxonomic characterization we propose the
43 placement of strain SP30^T as a new species within the genus *Spiribacter*, with the
44 name *Spiribacter aquaticus* sp. nov. The type strain is SP30^T (= CECT 9238^T = LMG
45 30005^T).

46

47 Hypersaline environments are widely distributed in the Earth. They are represented by
48 aquatic and saline terrestrial habitats, as well as salted products, such as salted foods or
49 marine or rock salt [1-3]. Most microbiological studies carried out in these environments
50 have been focused on saline aquatic systems. However many of these studies have been
51 based on culture-dependent techniques permitting for years the isolation of
52 microorganisms which not constitute the most abundant bacterial inhabitants in these
53 natural environments and therefore prevent the understanding of the relationships and
54 primary functions of the microorganisms in these natural environments [3-5].

55 Solar salterns traditionally used for the commercial production of salt are excellent
56 models for studying the microbial diversity, offering a wide range of salinities from
57 seawater to salt saturation. Santa Pola saltern, located on the East coast of Spain, is one
58 of the best known solar salterns worldwide. Numerous studies have been focused on this
59 multi-pond saltern, earlier based on the isolation and characterization of microorganisms
60 in pure cultures, later on culture-independent techniques and more recently on
61 metagenomics [6]. Metagenomics-based studies carried out in solar salterns located in
62 Spain [4-7] permitted the isolation of a new Gammaproteobacterium that appeared to be
63 a bacterial representative of the dominant microbial population at intermediate salinities
64 in these environments. It was taxonomically described as a new genus and species,
65 *Spiribacter salinus* [8]. The genus *Spiribacter* belongs to the family
66 *Ectothiorhodospiraceae*, within the order *Chromatiales*, class *Gammaproteobacteria* in
67 the phylum *Proteobacteria*. At the time of writing the genus *Spiribacter* comprises three
68 species, the above mentioned *Spiribacter salinus* [8], *Spiribacter curvatus* [9] and the
69 more recently described species *Spiribacter roseus* [10]. The complete genomes of all
70 species were sequenced [11], showing the smallest genomes described for a member of
71 the family *Ectothiorhodospiraceae*. Recent studies have shown evidence of the presence

72 of species of the genus *Spiribacter* worldwide [12-14], constituting a dominant group in
73 the concentrator ponds of solar salterns with intermediate salinities (10-25 % salts) [8].
74 The genus *Spiribacter* includes moderately halophilic species, Gram-stain-negative, non-
75 motile, curved rods-nearly closed rings to spiral-shaped cells at stationary phase and
76 producing pink-pigmented colonies [8].

77 The optimized culture conditions already used for the cultivation of the previously
78 described species of *Spiribacter* facilitate the isolation of new strains closely related to
79 this genus. In this sense during the course of studies on the microbial diversity of salterns
80 in the East coast of Spain a new halophilic microorganism, designated as strain SP30^T,
81 phylogenetically related to the genus *Spiribacter* was isolated. In this paper we describe
82 the isolation and characterization based on a polyphasic approach of this bacterium and
83 propose it as a new species of the genus *Spiribacter*.

84

85 Strain SP30^T was isolated from a water sample with 34.2 % (w/v) total salts obtained in
86 May 2015 from a pond of a marine saltern located in Santa Pola, Alicante, East coast of
87 Spain. Samples were collected in sterile containers, transported to the laboratory and
88 plated on 25 % seawater salts solution (SW) supplemented with 0.1 % yeast extract,
89 solidified with 2 % agar, and incubated at 37° C for one month. The 25 % SW solution
90 [described in 15] contained (g l⁻¹): NaCl, 195; MgCl₂·6H₂O, 34.6; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 49.5;
91 CaCl₂, 0.7; KCl, 5.0; NaHCO₃, 0.17; NaBr, 0.65. The pH was adjusted to pH 7.5 with 1
92 M KOH. The strain was isolated by direct loop-streaking the water sample on this medium
93 after incubation under aerobic conditions at 37 °C. The strain was routinely grown in
94 SMM medium previously used by León *et al.* [10] at 37 °C. The composition of the SMM
95 medium was (g l⁻¹): NaCl, 46.8; MgCl₂·6H₂O, 19.5; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 30.5; CaCl₂, 0.5; KCl,
96 3.0; NaHCO₃, 0.1; NaBr, 0.35; casein digest, 5.0 and sodium pyruvate, 1.1. The pH was

97 adjusted to 7.5 with 1 M KOH. Cultures were maintained at -80 °C in SMM medium
98 containing 30 % (v/v) glycerol. The type strains *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T, *Spiribacter*
99 *curvatus* UAH-SP71^T and *Spiribacter roseus* SSL50^T were used as reference strains for
100 comparative purposes in our study. They were cultivated under the same conditions than
101 the strain SP30^T.

102 For the determination of cellular morphology and motility, strain SP30^T was grown on
103 SMM medium on a shaking incubator at 200 rpm and examined by light microscopy
104 under a phase-contrast microscope (Olympus CX41). In the same way as with other
105 species of the genus *Spiribacter*, cells of strain SP30^T formed curved rods-nearly closed
106 rings and short spiral shapes, with a size of 0.4 (width) by 1.5 to 1.8 µm (length). In media
107 with higher salt concentrations the morphology of the curved cell rods became straighter.
108 Cells of the new isolate SP30^T were non-motile, Gram-stain-negative and strictly aerobic.
109 The morphology of the colonies, their size and pigmentation were observed on SMM
110 solid medium after 5 days of incubation at 37 °C. Colonies were circular, entire, yellow
111 to brown pigmented and 0.5-1.0 mm in diameter. Optimal conditions for growth were
112 determined by growing the strains in a modified SW liquid medium previously used by
113 León *et al.* [8], supplemented with sodium pyruvate and casein digest and lacking the
114 yeast extract, at 0, 3, 5, 7.5, 10, 12.5, 15, 17.5, 20, and 25 (w/v) NaCl. The pH range for
115 the isolate was tested under the optimal salt concentration conditions for the new strain,
116 adjusting the medium to pH 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 7.5, 8.0, 9.0, or 10.0 with the addition of the
117 appropriate buffers [16]. Growth rates were determined by monitoring the increase in the
118 optical density at 600 nm. The optimal and range of temperature were determined by
119 incubating the strain SP30^T at temperatures of 4, 15, 20, 28, 30, 37, 40 and 45 °C. The
120 strain SP30^T is a moderately halophilic bacterium able to grow in media with 7.5-25 %
121 (w/v) NaCl, with optimal growth at 12.5 % (w/v) NaCl. It is not able to grow in the

122 absence of NaCl. The pH range for growth was 7-9 showing the optimal growth at pH 8.
123 Cells were able to grow from 20 to 40 °C, with the optimal growth at 37 °C. All
124 biochemical tests were carried out in SMM medium at 37 °C, unless otherwise stated.
125 Growth under anaerobic conditions (with H₂/CO₂) was determined by incubation of strain
126 SP30^T in SMM solid medium in an anaerobic chamber using Anaerogen (Oxoid) to
127 generate anaerobic atmosphere and an anaerobic indicator (Oxoid). Catalase activity was
128 determined by adding a 1 % (w/v) H₂O₂ solution to colonies on SMM agar medium.
129 Oxidase activity was examined with 1 % (v/v) tetramethyl-p-phenylenediamine [17].
130 Hydrolysis of aesculin, casein, gelatin, DNA, starch or Tween 80, Voges-Proskauer and
131 methyl red tests, production of indole, phosphatase, urease, nitrate and nitrite reduction
132 were determined as described by Cowan & Steel [18]. Citrate utilization was determined
133 on Simmon's citrate medium supplemented with SMM medium lacking the pyruvate and
134 the casein digest. Acid production from carbohydrates was determined using a modified
135 phenol red base medium supplemented with 1 % of the carbohydrate, previously reported
136 by Ventosa *et al.* [19], supplemented with SMM medium lacking the pyruvate and
137 supplemented with casein digest instead of the yeast extract. The carbohydrates tested
138 were: L-arabinose, D-fructose, D-galactose, D-glucose, maltose, D-mannose, D-
139 melezitose, D-raffinose, D-ribose, D-trehalose and D-xylose. In order to determine the
140 range of substrates used as carbon and energy sources or as carbon, nitrogen and energy
141 sources, the classical medium of Koser [20] as modified by Ventosa *et al.* [19] was used.
142 Substrates were added as filter-sterilized solutions to give a final concentration of 1 g l⁻¹,
143 except for carbohydrates, which were used at 2 g l⁻¹. When the substrate was an amino
144 acid the basal medium was prepared without KNO₃ and (NH₄)₂HPO₄. The substrates
145 tested as sole source of carbon and energy were: D-arabinose, D-cellobiose, fructose, D-
146 galactose, D-glucose, lactose, maltose, D-mannose, D-melezitose, L-raffinose, D-

147 trehalose, D-mannitol, methanol, D-sorbitol, xylitol, benzoate, citrate, formate, hippurate,
148 pyruvate, succinate and D, L-tartrate. The following substrates were tested as sole source
149 of carbon, nitrogen and energy: L-alanine, L-arginine, L-asparagine, L-cysteine,
150 glutamine, L-isoleucine, L-lysine, L-methionine L-ornithine, L-phenylalanine, L-
151 threonine, L-serine and L-valine. Strain SP30^T showed catalase and oxidase activity.
152 Phosphatase and urease were positive for the new isolate. Gelatin, DNA, starch, Tween
153 80 and aesculin were not hydrolysed by the strain SP30^T. Nitrate was not reduced to
154 nitrite. Simmons' citrate test was negative and indole was not produced. Acid is produced
155 from D-ribose but is not produced from many other carbohydrates that have been tested
156 as for example D-glucose, D-trehalose, D-fructose, melezitose or maltose. As previously
157 reported for the other species of the genus *Spiribacter* [8-11], based on the analysis of the
158 complete genome as well as on the data obtained in the laboratory, strain SP30^T is
159 simplified in its metabolic versatility showing a very reduced ability to utilize organic
160 compounds. Of the compounds tested, only pyruvate in the presence of casein digest was
161 used as carbon and energy source. Differential characteristics between strain SP30^T and
162 other closely related species of the genus *Spiribacter* are listed in Table 1.

163 Genomic DNA from strain SP30^T was extracted and purified using the method described
164 by Marmur [21]. The 16S rRNA gene was amplified by PCR with the forward primer
165 16F27 and the reverse primer 16R1488 [22]. Direct determination of the sequence of the
166 PCR-amplified DNA was carried out using an automated DNA sequencer (model ABI
167 3130XL; Applied Biosystems). The almost-complete 16S rRNA gene sequence of strain
168 SP30^T (1,411 bp) was deposited in GenBank and used for initial BLAST searches in
169 GenBank and for phylogenetic analysis. The identification of phylogenetic neighbours
170 and the calculation of pairwise 16S rRNA gene sequence similarities were achieved using
171 the EzBioCloud tool [23]. The 16S rRNA gene sequence analysis showed that strain

172 SP30^T was a member of the genus *Spiribacter*. Its closest relatives were *Spiribacter*
173 *roseus* SSL50^T (99.9 % sequence similarity) and *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T (99.4
174 % sequence similarity). The 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity with the type species of
175 the genus *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T was 96.6 %. Other related species were
176 *Halopeptonella vilamensis* SV525^T (98.5 %), *Alkalilimnicola ehrlichii* MLHE-1^T
177 (95.4 %), *Arhodomonas aquaeolei* ATCC 49307^T (94.9 %) and *Arhodomonas recens*
178 RS91^T (94.9 %). The 16S rRNA gene sequence analysis was performed with the ARB
179 software package [24]. The 16S rRNA gene sequence was aligned with the published
180 sequences from closely related bacteria and the alignment was confirmed and checked
181 against both primary and secondary structures of the 16S rRNA molecule using the
182 alignment tool of the ARB software package. Phylogenetic trees were constructed using
183 three different methods: maximum-parsimony [25], neighbour-joining [26] and
184 maximum-likelihood [27] algorithms integrated in the ARB software for phylogenetic
185 inference. Bootstrap analysis was based on 1000 resamplings [28]. The 16S rRNA gene
186 sequences used for phylogenetic comparisons were obtained from the GenBank database
187 and their strain designations and accession numbers are shown in Fig. 1. The 16S rRNA-
188 based phylogenetic trees clustered the strain SP30^T into a branch that was clearly related
189 to the species of the genus *Spiribacter* and is further related to species of *Alkalilimnicola*
190 and *Arhodomonas*. Strain SP30^T was most closely related with the species *S. roseus* and
191 *S. curvatus*. The high similarity value with respect to *Spiribacter roseus* SSL50^T might
192 indicate that the new strain could constitute a member of this species. However,
193 significant differences in cultures of strain SP30^T regarding the species *Spiribacter*
194 *roseus*, and also *Spiribacter curvatus* were observed: strain SP30^T showed a brownish
195 yellow pigmentation instead the pink pigmentation showed by the species of *Spiribacter*.
196 Besides, the incubation time showed by this new strain was also shorter, reaching higher

197 optical densities than previously described species of *Spiribacter*. Thus, we decided to
198 investigate the new strain in more detail. Our phylogenetic analyses also show that the
199 species *Halopeptonella villamensis* is phylogenetically related to the species of
200 *Spiribacter* and it would be necessary to carry out a comparative study in order to
201 determine its exact taxonomic position.

202 The G+C content of the genomic DNA was determined from the midpoint value (T_m) of
203 the thermal denaturation profile [29] by using the equation of Owen & Hill [30], obtained
204 with a Perkin-Elmer UV-Vis Lambda 20 spectrophotometer at 260 nm equipped with a
205 PTP-1 peltier system programmed with an increasing of temperature of 1 °C/min. The
206 G+C content of the DNA for strain SP30^T was 65.4 mol%. This value is within the range
207 reported for species of the family *Ectothiorhodospiraceae* (50.5 to 69.9 mol%) [31] and
208 close to the G+C content of the DNA of the species *S. roseus* SSL50^T (64.2 %) [10].
209 DNA–DNA hybridization studies were performed by the competition procedure of the
210 membrane filter method [32]. The hybridization temperature used was 59.7 °C, which is
211 within the limit of validity for the filter method [33]. The percentage of hybridization was
212 calculated according to Johnson [32]. The experiments were carried out in triplicate. The
213 percentages of DNA-DNA hybridization (DDH) between strain SP30^T and *S. roseus*
214 SSL50^T and *Spiribacter curvatus* UAH-SP71^T were 40 %, and 55 %, respectively. These
215 DDH relatedness values were lower than 70 % threshold, accepted as the cut-off value
216 for species delineation [34, 35], indicating that the strain SP30^T constitutes a new species
217 of the genus *Spiribacter*.

218 Fatty acids analysis was performed using the MIDI Microbial Identification System [36].
219 Cells of strain SP30^T were cultured on SM15 agar medium at 37 °C [8] up to late
220 exponential phase, following the same methods described previously for the *Spiribacter*
221 species by León *et al.* [8-10]. The extraction and analysis of fatty acids were performed

222 according to the recommendations of the MIDI system. This analysis was carried out by
223 the CECT (Spanish Collection of Type Cultures, Valencia, Spain) using gas
224 chromatography (Agilent 6850) and a standardized protocol according to the MIDI
225 Sherlock system [37].

226 The cellular fatty acid profile of strain SP30^T was characterized by the fatty acids C_{16:0}
227 (31.9 %), C_{18:1 ω7c} (31.1 %), C_{19:0 cyclo ω8c} (9.9 %) and C_{12:0} (8.5 %) as the major fatty
228 acids (Table 2). The fatty acid composition of strain SP30^T is similar to those of the other
229 species of the genus *Spiribacter*. Nevertheless, there are some differences in the
230 proportion of some of the major fatty acids present in strain SP30^T compared to *S. roseus*
231 and *S. curvatus*, as it is for example the fatty acid C_{19:0 cyclo ω8c} which is present at
232 higher percentage in the new isolate SP30^T with respect to other species of *Spiribacter*.

233 On the basis of evidence obtained from the polyphasic taxonomic analysis it is proposed
234 that strain SP30^T should be considered as a novel species within the genus *Spiribacter*,
235 for which the name *Spiribacter aquaticus* sp. nov. is proposed.

236

237 **Description of *Spiribacter aquaticus* sp. nov.**

238 *Spiribacter aquaticus* (a.qua'ti.cus L. masc. adj. *aquaticus*, living or found in the water,
239 aquatic).

240 Cells are Gram-stain-negative, non-motile, aerobic, curved rods-nearly closed rings and
241 short spiral shapes with 0.4 x 1.5-1.8 μm. Colonies are circular, entire, yellow to brown
242 pigmented and 0.5-1.0 mm in diameter on SMM medium after 5 days of incubation at 37
243 °C. Moderately halophilic, able to grow in media with 7.5-25 % (w/v) NaCl, with optimal
244 growth at 12.5 % (w/v) NaCl. No growth occurs in the absence of NaCl. Able to grow in

245 the range of pH 7-9 and able to grow from 20 to 40 °C, with the optimal growth at pH 8
246 and at 37 °C. Catalase and oxidase positive. Gelatin, DNA, starch, Tween 80 and aesculin
247 are not hydrolysed. Nitrate is not reduced to nitrite. Phosphatase and urease are positive.
248 Simmons' citrate, methyl red and Voges-Proskauer tests are negative. Indole is not
249 produced. Acid is produced from D-ribose but not from D-arabinose, D-fructose, D-
250 galactose, D-glucose, maltose, D-mannose, D-melezitose, D-raffinose, D-trehalose and
251 D-xylose. Possess a very reduced ability to utilize organic compounds as sole carbon and
252 energy source. Pyruvate in the presence of casein digest is used as carbon and energy
253 source. The following compounds are not utilized as sole source of carbon and energy:
254 D-arabinose, D-cellobiose, fructose, D-galactose, D-glucose, lactose, maltose, D-
255 mannose, D-melezitose, L-raffinose, D-trehalose, D-mannitol, methanol, D-sorbitol,
256 xylitol, benzoate, citrate, formate, hippurate, succinate and D, L-tartrate. The following
257 compounds are not utilized as sole carbon, nitrogen and energy source: L-alanine, L-
258 arginine, L-asparagine, L-cysteine, glutamine, L-isoleucine, L-lysine, L-methionine L-
259 ornithine, L-phenylalanine, L-threonine, L-serine and L-valine. The major cellular fatty
260 acids are C_{16:0}, C_{18:1 ω7c}, C_{19:0 cyclo ω8c} and C_{12:0}. The DNA G+C content is 65.4 mol%.

261 The type strain is SP30^T (= CECT 9238^T = LMG 30005^T), isolated from the water of a
262 saltern pond located in Santa Pola, Alicante, Spain.

263

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273

274 **Conflict of interest**

275 The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

276

277 **Ethical statement**

278 No experimental work with animals or human has been carried out in this study.

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389 **Legend to figure**

390

391 **Fig. 1.** Neighbour-joining phylogenetic tree based on the 16S rRNA gene sequence
392 comparison showing the phylogenetic position of strain SP30^T and the closely related
393 species of the genus *Spiribacter* and other related genera. Sequence accession numbers
394 are shown in parentheses. Bootstrap values higher than 70 % are indicated at branch-
395 points. Filled circles indicate that the corresponding nodes were also obtained in the trees
396 generated with the maximum-likelihood and maximum-parsimony algorithms. The
397 species *Sulfurivirga caldicuralii* MM1^T was used as an outgroup. Bar, 0.01 substitutions
398 per nucleotide position.

399

400 **Table 1.** Differential characteristics of strain SP30^T and the type strain of the most closely
 401 related species of the genus *Spiribacter*.

402 Strains: 1, *Spiribacter aquaticus* SP30^T; 2, *Spiribacter roseus* SSL50^T; 3, *Spiribacter*
 403 *curvatus* UAH-SP71^T; 4, *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T.

404 All strains were Gram-stain-negative, non-motile, strictly aerobic, moderately halophilic
 405 bacteria, catalase and oxidase positive, not able to reduce nitrate or nitrite, and not able
 406 to hydrolyze gelatin, DNA, starch, Tween 80 or aesculin. +, Positive; -, negative.

407

Characteristic	1	2	3	4
Cell morphology	Curved rods-nearly closed rings, short spiral cells	Curved rods-nearly closed rings, short spiral cells	Thin curved rods, some spiral cells	Thin curved rods, long spiral cells
Colony pigmentation	Brownish yellow	Pink	Dark pink	Pink
Cell size (µm)	0.4 x 1.5-1.8	0.2-0.3 x 1.6-1.8	0.5-1.5	0.3 x 0.8-1.8
NaCl range (% w/v)	7.5-25	7.5-20	5-20	10-25
NaCl optimum (% w/v)	12.5	15.0	10.0	15.0
Temperature range for growth (°C)	20-40	15-40	5-40	15-40
pH range	7.0-9.0	7.0-9.0	5.0-10.0	6.0-9.0
pH optimum	8.0	7.5-8.0	8.0	7.5-8.0
Urease	+	+	-	+
Phosphatase	+	+	+	-
DNA G+C content (mol%)	65.4	64.2 (66.0*)	60.4 (63.9*)	60.0 (62.7*)

420 *Data from the genome sequence.

421

422 **Table 2.** Cellular fatty acid composition of strain SSL50^T and the most closely related
 423 species of the genus *Spiribacter*. All data were obtained under the same growth
 424 conditions. Values are percentages of the total cellular fatty acids. Strains: 1, strain SP30^T;
 425 2, *Spiribacter roseus* SSL50^T [10]; 3, *Spiribacter salinus* M19-40^T [8] and 4, *Spiribacter*
 426 *curvatus* UAH-SP71^T [9]. -, Values lower than 0.5 % or not detected.

Fatty acid	1	2	3	4	427
C _{9:0}	-	-	0.6	-	428
C _{10:0}	1.4	0.7	0.6	1.2	
C _{10:0} 3-OH	3.3	3.3	4.0	6.4	429
C _{12:0}	8.5	6.7	3.5	5.7	430
C _{12:0} 3-OH	3.2	3.1	1.3	1.2	
C _{14:1} ω5c	-	-	0.8	-	431
Summed feature 2*	-	-	-	2.0	432
Summed feature 3*	1.9	2.5	8.6	3.6	433
C _{14:0}	1.8	0.6	0.8	0.8	
C _{16:0}	31.9	28.3	9.3	13.4	434
Summed feature 8*	31.1 ⁺	50.0 [†]	60.6 [†]	60.6 [†]	435
C _{17:0}	-	-	1.8	-	
C _{17:1} ω8c	-	-	2.1	-	436
C _{17:1} ω6c	-	-	1.0	-	437
C _{18:0}	4.6	2.1	1.2	1.6	
C _{18:1} ω9c	-	0.8	-	-	438
Summed feature 7*	2.3	3.0	1.9	0.6	439
C _{19:0} cyclo ω8c	9.9	3.9	1.0	2.2	

440

441 * Summed features are groups of two or three fatty acids that could not be separated by
 442 GC with the MIDI system. Summed feature 3 comprised C_{16:1} ω6c and/or C_{16:1} ω7c,
 443 summed feature 7 comprised un 18.846/C_{19:1} ω6c and summed feature 8 comprised C_{18:1}

444 $\omega 6c$ and/or $C_{18:1} \omega 7c$. ⁺ This percentage corresponds to $C_{18:1} \omega 7c$; [†] This percentage
445 corresponds to a mixture of $C_{18:1} \omega 7c$ and/or $C_{18:1} \omega 6c$.

446

